

A COMPRESSIVE STUDY OF MULTIFUNCTIONAL AND THERAPEUTIC POTENTIAL OF BUTTERFLY PEA

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ABSTRACT

The review study investigates the nutritional, medicinal, and therapeutic advantages of Butterfly Pea (*Clitoria ternatea* L.), a plant that belongs to the Fabaceae family and is indigenous to Southeast Asia and other tropical regions. Various parts of the plant, *Clitoria ternatea*, have been used in Ayurvedic medicine for a long time. Many of the plant's phytochemicals, such as flavonoids, polyacylated compounds, and anthocyanins, have been shown to have anti-inflammatory, anti-cancer, anti-obesity, and anti-diabetic properties. The medicinal and agricultural uses of *Clitoria ternatea*, a perennial legume commonly known as butterfly pea, have attracted a lot of attention lately. Innovative treatments for a variety of diseases have been developed with the help of herbal substances. To improve herbal discoveries in the pharmaceutical industry, a number of novel technical strategies have been studied. Herbal formulations have excellent patient compliance, delivery rates,

and efficacy when used to treat a range of disorders. Extracts from plants and herbs are well known for their therapeutic potential and have been used to treat a wide range of serious illnesses all over the world.

KEYWORDS: Aparajita, multipurpose uses, bioactive compounds.

INTRODUCTION

Past ten years herbal remedies have grown significantly over the allopathy medicines. Because they contain active ingredients that function as natural antimicrobial agents, plants are an excellent source for treating a variety of illnesses.^[1] In addition to herbal extracts, plants have the ability to cure people and have been used to treat a number of serious illnesses worldwide, which has made them well-known. The foundation of Ayurvedic medicine is primarily plants. The foundation of Siddha and Unani medicine is plants.^[2]

Millions of people around the world today use drugs derived from plants as traditional treatments for a wide range of illnesses. Medicinal plants have been shown to have many therapeutic benefits. Plants present the possibility of an alternative strategy when looking for new drugs.^[3] *Clitoria Ternatea Linn* is its common name; it was originally known as Breyne, butterfly pea, Aparajita, Shankhpushpi, bluepea, and cordofan-pea⁶. Butterfly pea is another name for *Clitoria ternatea*. The plant belongs to the family Fabaceae. About 60 species of *Clitoria ternatea* are found in the tropical belt, while a few species are found in temperate regions.^[4]

Clitoria ternatea is a herbaceous perennial legume that is hardy and tenacious. It is said that almost every part of this plant has therapeutic properties. The flowers of this plant have been used in religious ceremonies since ancient times. Here, they had served several of these functions. The plant has long been used to treat a variety of ailments, including tonsillitis, skin conditions, vermicide, cough, asthma, infertility, and digestive disorders. Anthelminthic, anti-hyperglycemic, anti-inflammatory, anti-diarrheal, antioxidant, hepatoprotective, immunomodulatory, anti-histamic, and cholinergic activity are just a few of the medicinal properties that numerous researchers assessed. In addition to being a good "Medhya," *Clitoria ternatea* is also said to be effective in treating asthma, severe bronchitis, and hectic fever. It is also said to be a treatment for snakebite and scorpion sting. *Clitoria ternatea* new flower was used in an early study. This study demonstrated lipid-lowering effects.^[5]

Clitoria ternatea pharmacological properties have a broad range of therapeutic applications, including antimicrobial, antioxidant, anticarcinogenic, hypolipidemic, cardioprotective, neuroprotective, anti-inflammatory, analgesic, antipyretic, hypoglycemic, and gastroprotective effects. Numerous bioactive substances, including tannins, saponins, flavonoids, alkaloids, anthocyanins, glycosides, volatile oils, and steroids, are found in plants, according to phytochemical studies. These substances work together to partially explain its

various biological actions and possible therapeutic applications.^[6] Because oral antimicrobial agents have limitations, a topical gel formulation of *Clitoria ternatea* flower extract (CTFE) was created as a substitute. The gel's antimicrobial properties against *Bacillus* species included pentacyclic triterpenoids (taraxerol, taraxerone) and anthocyanins (ternatin).^[7]

Plant profile

Binomial name: *Clitoria ternatea* L.

Kingdom: Plantae

Clade: Tracheophytes

Clade: Angiosperms

Clade: Eudicots

Description of *Clitoria ternatea*

Habit: Twining climber

Root: Branched tap root system having nodules

Stem: Aerial, weak stem and a twiner.

Fig. 1: *Clitoria ternatea* Leaves and Flower.

BOTANY AND PHARMACOGNOSY OF *CLITORIA TERNATEA*

Clitoria ternatea is a type of legume plant, which means it has certain features common to plants in the legume family. It has special blue flowers that give it its common name. This plant is a climbing shrub that can grow up to 2 to 3 meters tall. It can be found growing in gardens or in wild areas and has bright blue or white flowers that look like conch shells. Even though it probably originated in America, it is now grown and has become naturalized in the humid tropics below 1600 meters in both the old and new worlds, as noted by Morton in

1981. It grows in places like South and Central America, the Caribbean, Madagascar, India, the Philippines, and other tropical countries in Asia.^[8,9] In India, it is grown either on its own or mixed with other long-lived grasses in regions such as Punjab, Rajasthan, Uttar Pradesh, Gujarat, Maharashtra, Madhya Pradesh, Andhra Pradesh, Tamil Nadu, and Karnataka. This plant helps control many stubborn weeds and also improves the soil by capturing and adding nitrogen.^[10]

MORPHOLOGICAL CHARACTERS

It contains elliptic, obtuse leaves and is a perennial herbaceous plant. It thrives in moist, neutral soil and grows as a vine or creeper. This plant's white flowers, which are solitary and have light yellow markings, they are about 4 cm long by 3 cm wide. Some varieties yield deep blue flowers. The fruits are 5-7 cm long. flat pods that contain six to ten seeds each. When they are soft, they can be eaten. It requires little care when grown and is used as a revegetation species and ornamental plant in places like Australian coal mines. This plant is also used to improve soil quality through the decomposition of nitrogen-rich plant material because, as a legume, its roots form a symbiotic association with soil bacteria called rhizobia, which convert atmospheric N₂ into a form that plants can use (a process known as nitrogen fixing).^[11]

Vernacular name^[11]

Table No. 1: The taxonomical classification of *Clitoria ternatea* L species.

Sanskrit	Girikarnika, Vishnukranta
Assamese	Aparajita
Bengali	Aparajita
English	<i>Clitoria</i>
Gujarati	Gokarni
Hindi	Aparajita
Marathi	Gokarna, Aparajita
Malayalam	Shankhapushapam
Punjabi	Koyal
Tamil	Kakkanam

The taxonomical classification of *Clitoria ternatea* species

Table NO. 2: Scientific Classification of *Clitoria ternatea* L.

Class	Magnoliopsida
Sub Class	Rosidae
Order	Fabales
Family	Fabaceae
Genus	<i>Clitoria</i>

Species	<i>ternatea</i> (Linnaeus)
Botanical name	<i>Clitoria ternatea</i> L.
Common name	Asian pigeon wings

GEOGRAPHY AND DISTRIBUTION

This plant is majorly found in Asia, including locations in South Asia and Southeast Asia but has also been introduced to Africa, Australia and the Americas. Its geographic range spans across diverse climatic zones, predominantly thriving in tropical and subtropical climates where it contributes to both agricultural productivity and ecological balance.^[10]

CHEMICAL CONSTITUENTS AND MEDICINAL USES

The initial check for plant chemicals showed that the plant has tannins, phlobatannins, carbohydrates, saponins, triterpenoids, phenols, flavanoids, flavonol glycosides, proteins, alkaloids, anthraquinone, anthocyanins, cardiac glycosides, Stigmast-4-ene-3, 6-dione, volatile oils, and steroids.^[12]

1. Leaves: The leaves have 21.5% crude fiber and 21.5 to 29% protein.

From the leaves, clitorin and kaempferol were found. The leaves also contain 3-monoglucoside, 3-rutinoside, 3-neohesperidoside, 3-o-rhamnosyl-glucoside, 3-o-rhamnosylgalactoside of kaempferol, as well as kaempferol-3-o-rhamnosyl-rhamnosyl glucoside. They also include aparajitin and β -sitosterol. The flowers, which are blue in color, contain delphinidin-3,5-diglucoside, delphinidin-3 β -glucoside, and its 3-methyl form, malvidin-3 β -glucoside, kaempferol, and cyanidin chloride. A lactone called aparajitin was isolated from the leaves.^[13]

Uses: To treat headaches and swollen glands, the juice of *Clitoria ternatea* leaves is combined with salt and applied around the ears. This lessens discomfort. Additionally, the juice is used as a snake bite remedy. The roots, seeds, and leaves of *Clitoria ternatea* are commonly used as a brain tonic in traditional medicine, particularly in Ayurveda. They are thought to enhance intelligence and memory.^[14]

2. Root: The roots have taxaxerol and taxaxerone. The bark of the roots contains resin, tannin, starch, and flavonol glycosides. The root nodule contains glycine, alanine, valine, leucine, α -aminobutyric acid, aspartic acid, glutamic acid, arginine, ornithine, histidine, and γ -aminobutyric acid.^[12]

Uses: *Clitoria ternatea* roots are used as a diuretic. Numerous medical conditions, including fever, arthritis, constipation, indigestion, and eye disorders, are treated with the root. It is also used to treat skin conditions, sore throats, ascites, and enlargement of the abdominal organs. When chronic bronchitis is present, it is administered. The roots are frequently given to kids as a general tonic with honey and ghee to enhance their cognitive function, muscular strength, and skin tone. Additionally, it treats mental illnesses and epilepsy.^[9]

3. Seed: The seed has a bitter acid resin as its main active part, along with fixed oil, tannic acid, and glucose. It also has a cotyledon that is rich in granular starch and tastes bitter. Two chemicals, Sitosterol and anthoxanthin, have been taken out from the seeds. When seed oil is processed, it gives palmitic, stearic, oleic, linoleic, and linolenic acids. Oils from blue and white-flower varieties have almost the same composition. Seeds also have cinnamic acid, hexacosanol, and nucleoprotein, which has an amino acid sequence somewhat like insulin. The seeds are very high in protein, with 15 to 25% of their content being protein. They also have p-hydroxycinnamic acid, flavonol-3-glycoside, ethyl- α -D-galactopyranoside, adenosine, 3,5,7,4-tetrahydroxyflavone-3-rhamnoglucoside, polypeptide, hexacosanol, and oligosaccharides or flatulene. A food dye called delphinidin 3,3',5'-triglucoside has also been found in seeds. Lecin makes up about 2.8% of the total extractable protein from the seed meal, which is 30 mg of lectin per 30 grams of *Clitoria ternatea* seeds. This is compared to 9 mg of fetuin per 30 grams of seeds. Tryptophan and tyrosine are also found in the seeds.^[12]

Uses: The seeds are used to treat abdominal organ swelling, dropsy, and colic. They are also applied to swollen joints. For three days, fifty grams of crushed seeds are taken once daily with a cup of water. The seeds are boiled in water in Bangladesh's Rajshahi district, and the resulting liquid is subsequently strained through a cloth. To treat urinary problems, one-third of a kilogram of the strained liquid is taken for seven days. For constipation, a blend of pepper and *Clitoria ternatea* seed powder is used.^[15]

4. Flower: Two types of acyl groups were found in the flower, namely E-4-O- β -D-glucopyranosyl-p-coumaric acid and 6-O-malonyl-D-glucopyranose.

Six other compounds, called ternatins (A1, A2, B1, B2, D1, and D2), were isolated using reverse phase HPLC. The white flower only contains kaempferol. From the petals of *Clitoria ternatea* L. The flower also contains kaempferol 3-2G-rhamnosylrutinoside; kaempferol 3-neohesperidoside, quercetin 3-neohesperidoside; myricetin 3-neohesperidoside; kaempferol

3-rutinoside; quercetin 3-rutinoside; myricetin 3-rutinoside; kaempferol 3-glucoside; quercetin 3-glucoside; and myricetin 3-glucoside. Cyanine chloride and kaempferol have been isolated and identified from the flowers. Six acylated anthocyanins (A, B, C, D, E, and F) were isolated from blue flowers, with some partial characterization of kaempferol and its 3-glucoside, robinin, quercetin and 3-glucoside, and ternatins A and B. Blue flowers also contain lobelinins, which have a 3,5,3',5'-tetraglucoside pattern. Deacylternatin has also been reported in blue flower petals. Different lines of *Clitoria ternatea* with different petal colors have been studied for flavonoids. A new glucoside, Delphinidin 3-O-(2''-O- α -rhamnosyl-6''-O-malonyl)- β -glucoside, was found in the petals of the mauve line. A group of ternatins was also identified in all blue petal lines, which includes 15 (poly) acylated delphinidin. White petal lines do not contain anthocyanins. Ternatins are found in all blue petal lines, which are 3',5'-disubstituted polyacylanthocyanins. The mauve petal line instead accumulates delphinidin 3-O-(6''-O-myl)- β -glucoside. Researchers found that the difference in color, from blue to mauve, comes from the lack of (polyacylated) glucosyl group substitutions at both the 3'- and 5'-positions of ternatins, not from a change in the structure of an anthocyanidin from delphinidin.^[12]

Uses: *Clitoria ternatea* flowers are used to make a paste that is used to treat headaches and eye infections. Additionally, the flowers are used as a snake bite remedy. Between the two types, the white-flowered one is more effective for treatment and is preferred. Typically, the blue-flowered type is substituted for the white-flowered one.^[11]

Pharmacological activity of *Clitoria ternatea* (CT)

Clitoria ternatea has been tested a lot for its different medicine effects. It has clear effects on the brain and nervous system, like increasing acetylcholine levels and helping with memory, reducing stress, calming anxiety, treating depression, preventing seizures, making you relaxed, and helping you sleep. These qualities make it useful for treating brain and nervous system problems in Ayurvedic medicine (Sections 6.1–6.5). It also has other helpful properties like fighting germs, reducing fever, lowering inflammation, easing pain, helping the body get rid of extra water, acting as a local numbing agent, controlling blood sugar, and killing insects.^[16]

1. Wound healing effect

Using excision, incision, and dead-space models, the wound-healing properties of *Clitoria ternatea* seed and root extracts were studied. Orally administered by gavage and topically

applied as ointment, extracts from the seeds and roots of *Clitoria ternatea* significantly improved wound healing in excision, incision, and dead-space models. The conclusion of the study also showed that *Clitoria ternatea* affected all three stages: inflammatory, proliferative and remodeling phases of wound healing.^[17]

2. Nootropic activity

Traditional Ayurvedic medicine uses *Clitoria ternatea* (CT), which has strong nootropic and neuroprotective properties. By altering the amount of acetylcholine (ACh) and the activity of acetylcholinesterase (AChE) in various brain regions, aerial and root extracts both enhance memory retention in animal models.^[18] It was discovered that root extracts were more successful than aerial parts at reducing memory impairments, particularly when taken in larger dosages. Long-lasting behavioral improvements, elevated hippocampus ACh levels, and increased dendritic arborization of amygdala neurons were observed in studies conducted on neonatal and young rats, which may indicate the involvement of BDNF/NGF-like substances. In models of diabetes and Alzheimer's disease, extracts also protected neurons and encouraged neurogenesis. Ethanolic and hydro-alcoholic extracts demonstrated cholinesterase inhibition, decreased oxidative stress, and inhibited enzymes associated with Alzheimer's disease.^[19] *Clitoria ternatea* formulations improved memory, learning, and neuroprotection, either by themselves or in combination (e.g., with *Salacia reticulata*).

3. Anticonvulsant activity

Clitoria ternatea may have anticonvulsant properties. Its aerial parts methanolic extract (100 mg/kg, p.o.) significantly reduced tonic hind limb extension in maximal electroshock (MES) induced seizures in mice and delayed the onset of seizures in pentylenetetrazole (PTZ) models, suggesting antiepileptic potential through GABAergic modulation. However, in rats' PTZ and MES models, higher doses of ethanolic extract (230 and 460 mg/kg, p.o.) did not exhibit any protective effects, indicating that efficacy varies by extract type, dose, and species.^[20]

4. Antidepressant activity

Clitoria ternatea has strong antidepressant properties. In mice, methanolic extract of aerial parts (100 and 400 mg/kg, p.o.) decreased immobility in the tail suspension test; the higher dose had a stronger effect than fluoxetine. Additionally, ethanolic root extract (150–300 mg/kg) showed antidepressant properties. The plant has the potential to be used in the development of herbal treatments for anxiety and depression because bioactive compounds

from *Clitoria ternatea* roots, such as n-hexadecanoic acid and (Z)-9, 17-octadecadienal, exhibit potential as selective MAO-A inhibitors.^[21]

5. Anti-anxiety effect

In the elevated plus maze and light/dark exploration tests, *Clitoria ternatea* showed a weak anti-anxiety effect. When given to mice 60 minutes prior to the test, the methanolic extract of *Clitoria ternatea* has demonstrated a dose-dependent anti-anxiety effect (100–400 mg/kg, p.o.). The amount of time spent in the open arm increased dose-dependently with oral *Clitoria ternatea* administration (100–400 mg/kg). Higher doses of *Clitoria ternatea* (100, 200, and 400 mg/kg, p.o.) lengthened the time spent in the lit box in the light/dark exploration test. In a dose-dependent manner, the amount of time spent in the dark box decreased.^[20]

6. Anti-ulcer activity

By calculating the ulcer index in a rat's stomach, the anti-stress properties of *Clitoria ternatea* were assessed in cold restraint stress-induced ulcers. The rats were strapped to a wooden plank and kept at 4°C for two hours in order to cause ulcers. When given to mice 60 minutes prior to the test, the methanolic extract of *Clitoria ternatea* demonstrated a dose-dependent anti-stress effect at 100, 200, and 400 mg/kg, p.o. Because of its anti-secretory and antioxidant properties, the ethanolic and chloroform extracts of *Clitoria ternatea* leaves as well as the alcoholic and aqueous extract of the entire plant also showed anti-ulcer effects in rats.^[22]

7. Analgesic activity

Clitoria ternatea exhibits strong analgesic effects. Although they had no effect on acetic acid-induced writhing, ethanolic aerial extracts (230 and 460 mg/kg) demonstrated mild activity in the tail clip test and notable effects in the radiant heat test (30 minutes to 3 hours). Methanolic root extracts (200 and 400 mg/kg), on the other hand, demonstrated a strong peripheral analgesic effect by significantly reducing writhing by 50.1% and 63.8%, respectively. Additionally, methanolic extracts of *Clitoria ternatea* root and leaves exhibited antinociceptive properties; in the acetic acid-induced writhing test, leaf extracts were effective.^[23]

8. Local anaesthetic effect

Using plexus anesthesia in frogs and corneal anesthesia in rabbits, the local anesthetic effect of the ethanolic extract of *Clitoria ternatea's* aerial parts was assessed. They discovered that

a 10% solution of *Clitoria ternatea* extract eliminated the frog's foot withdrawal reflex while having no surface anesthetic effect on the rabbit's cornea.^[16]

9. Antipyretic effect

Clitoria ternatea has strong antipyretic properties. Similar to chlorpromazine, ethanolic aerial extracts (230 and 460 mg/kg,) decreased normal body temperature and demonstrated dose-dependent effects in yeast-induced pyrexia. In rats with yeast-induced fever, methanolic root extracts also showed potent antipyretic effects, and 400 mg/kg of ethanolic and acetone leaf extracts also decreased fever.^[16]

10. Anti-inflammatory activity

Clitoria ternatea exhibits potent anti-inflammatory properties. Carrageenan-induced paw edema and acetic acid-induced vascular permeability were inhibited by methanolic root extract with 400 mg/kg exhibiting effects similar to those of diclofenac. Additionally, it decreased peritoneal inflammation by as much as 55.1%. In vitro activity was also demonstrated by ethanolic leaf and flower extracts. Bioactive substances like ternatin anthocyanins and quercetin glycosides inhibited COX-2, decreased ROS, blocked NFκB translocation, and decreased the production of iNOS and NO, thereby suppressing LPS-induced inflammation. These results point to *Clitoria ternatea's* potential for creating treatments for long-term inflammatory conditions.^[24]

11. Anti-asthmatic activity

By preventing dye leakage in passive cutaneous anaphylaxis in rats, preventing mast cell degranulation caused by egg albumin, and lowering milk-induced leukocytosis and eosinophilia in mice, ethanolic root extracts of *Clitoria ternatea* showed strong anti-asthmatic activity. The extract also demonstrated bronchodilator effects, indicating that it may be used to treat asthma.^[25]

12. Antihyperglycemic and antihyperlipidemic effects

In experimental diabetes models, *Clitoria ternatea* significantly reduces hyperglycemia and hyperlipidemia. In alloxan-induced diabetic rats, aqueous extracts of flowers and leaves (400 mg/kg, 84 days) increased serum insulin, HDL-cholesterol, liver, and muscle glycogen while decreasing blood glucose, glycosylated hemoglobin, cholesterol, triglycerides, urea, and creatinine. By increasing glucokinase and decreasing glucose-6-phosphatase activity, the extracts also restored normalcy to liver enzymes. By increasing biliary excretion and

decreasing cholesterol absorption, hydroalcoholic root and seed extracts demonstrated anti-hyperlipidemic effects. In STZ-induced diabetes, ethanolic seed extract and methanolic leaf extract (single dose, 15 days) demonstrated antidiabetic effects. In alloxan-induced diabetes, ethanolic flower extract inhibited β -galactosidase (55.26%) and α -glucosidase (24.87%), lowering serum sugar by 41.48%. Furthermore, in young diabetic rats, defatted alcoholic root extract (100 mg/kg, 30 days) preserved the pancreatic and hippocampus CA3 tissues. Aqueous leaf extract (100 mg/kg, 14 days) decreased blood glucose in diabetic rats, whereas aqueous flower petal extract prevented fructose-induced protein glycation. In vitro antidiabetic activity was also shown by ethanolic extracts of leaves and flowers. All things considered, *Clitoria ternatea* exhibits great promise for the treatment of diabetes and its aftereffects, such as oxidative stress, hyperlipidemia, and damage from glycation.^[26]

13. Hepatoprotective activity

By lowering aspartate aminotransferase, alanine aminotransferase, and bilirubin levels and improving histopathological outcomes, mice given a 200 mg/kg, p.o. dose of *Clitoria ternatea* leaf methanolic extract demonstrated protection against paracetamol-induced liver toxicity. Rats with carbon tetrachloride-induced hepatotoxicity were used in a prior study to assess the hepatoprotective potential of white- and blue-flowered *Clitoria ternatea* leaf extract. Because of its possible antioxidant effect, they discovered that the extract from white-flowered *Clitoria ternatea* leaves had a greater hepato-protective effect than that from blue-flowered *Clitoria ternatea* leaves.^[27]

14. Immunomodulatory activity

Reduced immune cell sensitization, immune cell presentation, and phagocytosis may be the cause of the immunomodulatory effect observed in the alcoholic extract of *Clitoria ternatea* root and hydroalcoholic extract of *Clitoria ternatea* seed. Human monocytes' secretion of different cytokines and chemokines was decreased by cationic cliotides from *Clitoria ternatea* in both resting and lipopolysaccharide-stimulated conditions, indicating that *Clitoria ternatea* may be a viable option for new immunomodulating treatments. This immunomodulatory effect might also be caused by *Clitoria ternatea*'s anti-inflammatory and antioxidant qualities.^[28]

15. Platelet aggregation inhibitory activity

Assessed the anthocyanin ternatin D1 that was separated from *Clitoria ternatea* flowers for its ability to inhibit platelets in rabbits in vitro. According to the authors, ternatin D1 significantly reduced platelet aggregation brought on by adenine diphosphate and collagen.^[16]

16. Antioxidant activity

Across all extracts, *Clitoria ternatea* demonstrates potent antioxidant activity. Significant free radical scavenging and protection against protein and lipid peroxidation were demonstrated by methanolic, acetone, aqueous, and ethanolic extracts of leaves and flowers. While methanolic leaf extract restored antioxidant enzymes (SOD, CAT, and GPx) under aluminum-induced oxidative stress, aqueous flower extract also shielded rats' testicles from damage caused by ketoconazole. The activity of *Clitoria ternatea* is influenced by non-enzymatic antioxidants like ascorbic acid, reduced glutathione, and carotenoids.^[29]

17. Anti-cancer potential

In comparison to seed and stem-bark, methanolic leaf extract of *Clitoria ternatea* exhibits the highest level of cytotoxicity and anticancer potential (LC₅₀: 25.82 µg/ml). Even more potent was its methanol fraction (LC₅₀: 22.28 µg/ml). Aqueous flower extract, methanolic flower and seed extracts, and other solvent fractions have also been shown to be cytotoxic. While seed extract decreased tumor growth and increased mouse survival, *Clitoria ternatea* cyclotides increased chemosensitivity in resistant lung cancer cells. These results demonstrate *Clitoria ternatea* potential as a source for the creation of anticancer medications.^[30]

18. Anti-microbial activity

A possible substitute for antibiotics due to its broad-spectrum antimicrobial activity is *Clitoria ternatea*. While petroleum ether, ethyl acetate, and particularly methanolic leaf extracts were effective against *B. cereus*, *S. aureus*, *K. pneumoniae*, *P. vulgaris*, and *S. typhi*, aqueous flower extract demonstrated activity against dental caries bacteria. Finotin, a seed protein, exhibited insecticidal and antimicrobial qualities. Pathogenic *E. coli*, *K. pneumoniae*, and *P. aeruginosa* were inhibited by flower extracts (aqueous, methanol, and chloroform). Additionally, leaf extracts demonstrated efficacy against fish pathogens. Furthermore, hydroalcoholic leaf extracts showed antifungal activity, and *Clitoria ternatea* cyclotides demonstrated gram-negative-specific antibacterial effects.^[28]

19. Anthelmintic activity

The ethanolic extract of *Clitoria ternatea* leaves exhibited anthelmintic activity at 100 mg/ml, whereas the methanolic extract demonstrated activity at lower concentrations (10–25 mg/ml). At those lower concentrations, however, the ethanolic extract exhibited no activity.^[16]

20. Other pharmacological activities

The pharmacological activities of *Clitoria ternatea* are varied. Standardized leaf extract supports the potential for wound healing by exhibiting hyaluronidase and MMP-1 inhibitory effects. Against mosquito vectors, methanolic extracts of leaves, roots, flowers, and seeds showed larvicidal activity; the most effective extracts were from the seeds. Due to their antioxidant qualities, ethanolic aerial extracts demonstrated nephroprotective effects in acetaminophen-induced toxicity. Furthermore, mice showed anti-diarrheal activity (methanolic extract) and a purgative effect (ethanolic and acetone extracts) from *Clitoria ternatea* leaves. There have also been reports of *Clitoria ternatea* root's diuretic effects in dogs.^[32]

Formulations of *Clitoria ternatea*

1. Antimicrobial gel

A novel topical antimicrobial gel was developed using flower extracts from *Clitoria ternatea* (CTFE) in order to overcome the drawbacks of oral formulations. Phytoconstituents like anthocyanins (ternatin) and pentacyclic triterpenoids (taraxerol, taraxerone) were credited with the gel's strong antimicrobial activity against *Bacillus* species. Optimized formulations demonstrated good drug release, in vitro diffusion, stability, pH, and spreadability. Carbapol 934P and HPMC K100M enhanced antibacterial activity in concert. Overall, the CTFE gel was found to be effective, safe, and stable for topical use.^[12]

2. Antiaging cream

The formulation of the polyherbal cream was based on the antioxidant activity of specific plant extracts. The cream was made with natural herbal ingredients like *Clitoria Ternatea* (butterfly pea), *Mangifera indica* (mango), and *Annona squamosa* (custard apple). *Mangifera indica* and *Annona squamosa* were extracted by cold maceration (hydroalcoholic extraction) with distilled water and ethanol as a solvent. *Clitoria Ternatea* was extracted by hot water extraction with distilled water as a solvent.^[33]

3. Antifungal cream

Clitoria ternatea's effectiveness as an antifungal drug for vaginal infections. Herbal creams that, in contrast to standard formulation (MCC), can be used to treat vaginal infections.^[34]

4. Hair serum

Cyanthillium cinereum and *Clitoria ternatea* (butterfly pea flower) extracts were used to create and test a hair serum meant to address dandruff. The problem was the need for a natural, safe alternative to synthetic dandruff treatments. The abundance of phytochemicals, such as phenolic acids, flavonoids, alkaloids, and anthocyanins, led to the selection of both plants. These substances are antifungal, antioxidant, and beneficial to the scalp. The extracts were made by aqueous maceration and then mixed with excipients like glycerine, xanthan gum, lavender oil, tween 80, phenoxy ethanol, and rose water to make a serum formulation. The serum's physical characteristics, homogeneity, pH, viscosity, spreadability, antifungal activity, and stability were evaluated. Serum helps maintain healthy scalps, prevents dandruff, and reduces the risk of negative side effects associated with chemical formulations.^[35]

5. Emulgel

Emulgels combine the benefits of emulsions and gels to improve the skin adherence, absorption, and bioavailability of hydrophobic drugs and plant extracts. *Clitoria ternatea*, which is rich in antioxidant anthocyanins, and *Nyctanthes arbor-tristis*, which contains anti-inflammatory iridoid glycosides, were selected for formulation. When combined in an emulgel base, they may have synergistic antioxidant and anti-inflammatory effects, making it a promising treatment for topical conditions.^[36]

6. Antidiabetic green tea

Clitoria ternatea whole plant, extract-based green tea formulation with anti-diabetic properties. *Clitoria ternatea* leaf extract, among other ingredients, is used in this formulation as an antidiabetic. Alpha amylase and glucosidase assays were used to assess the formulation in vitro. Additional analyses included physiochemical and organoleptic properties (such as the solubility test, pH, ash value, LOD test, and extract values that are soluble in water and alcohol, etc.). The formulation achieved an anti-diabetic effect and met the requirements for an antidiabetic formulation. It demonstrated the preparation's potential as an easy-to-use antidiabetic. People with diabetes, obesity, and digestive issues can benefit greatly from drinking this tea.^[37]

7. Anti-Inflammatory gel

Created a new topical herbal gel with anti-inflammatory properties using leaves from *Clitoria ternatea*. *Clitoria ternatea* leaf ethyl acetate extract was used to create the gel. Numerous evaluation criteria, including physicochemical parameters, pH, viscosity, spreadability, homogeneity, grittiness, extrudability, skin irritation, stability study, and anti-inflammatory activity, were applied to the prepared gels. The bioactive ethylacetate extract of *Clitoria ternatea* leaves was successfully used to create a topical gel. The gel was found to be very effective as anti-inflammatory formulations.^[38]

8. Anti-dandruff Shampoo

Clitoria ternatea shampoo was well-tolerated by patients and demonstrated similar efficacy in reducing the severity of dandruff; 20% *Clitoria ternatea* shampoo was associated with fewer side effects. *Clitoria ternatea* shampoo was well-tolerated by patients and demonstrated similar efficacy in reducing the severity of dandruff; 20% *Clitoria ternatea* shampoo was associated with fewer side effects.^[39]

9. Facial wash gel

The creation and description of herbal cosmetic face wash. In the past, women were highly self-conscious about their appearance and began dressing to enhance it. Propylene glycol, sodium lauryl sulfate, and preservatives were thoroughly dissolved in a small amount of water. Carbopol was gradually added to the above solution and thoroughly mixed until a gel-like dispersion was achieved. To achieve a complete gel-like consistency, the extracts were added one at a time. Finally, triethanolamine was added.^[40]

10. Nasal spray

The Butterfly Pea Flower (*Clitoria ternatea*) is the basis for the nasal spray formulation, which exhibits neuroprotective, antioxidant, and cognitive-enhancing properties. The nasal pathway improves treatment response by allowing drugs to enter the brain through neural pathways rather than the blood-brain barrier. Along with consistent drug release patterns and good nasal mucosal barrier penetration, the developed formulation demonstrated desirable chemical properties. Through enhanced cognition and disease speed control, the discovery indicates that a nasal spray derived from Butterfly Pea Flower has potential as an alternative herbal therapy for Alzheimer's disease.^[41]

11. Anti-obesity herbal drink

Although their effectiveness is still up for debate, herbal drinks have also been used to treat obesity. Flavonoids and anthocyanins, which have anti-obesity properties, are found in herbal drink products like lemon juice and butterfly pea flower extract. This study aimed to develop herbal beverage for the treatment of obesity and assess its acceptability, nutritional value, phytochemical content, and microbiological contamination. The herbal drink's acceptability was evaluated using an organoleptic test. In conclusion, herbal beverages may develop into a substitute for traditional anti-obesity therapies.^[42]

12. Herbal sunscreen

Creation of an herbal sunscreen with extract from *Clitoria ternatea*, or blue pea flower, which is well-known for its strong antioxidant and photoprotective qualities. Natural excipients were used to incorporate the extract into a cream-based formulation. Presence of phenolic compounds, flavonoids, and anthocyanins, which enhance the plant's capacity to absorb UV light. The prepared formulations underwent a number of physicochemical tests, such as spectrophotometric analysis to determine the Sun Protection Factor (SPF), stability, spreadability, and pH. Herbal sunscreen showed a moderate SPF value, acceptable aesthetic qualities, and desirable stability, indicating its effectiveness as a natural UV protection substitute.^[43]

13. Herbal face pack

The purpose of this study is to create and assess a herbal face pack made with *Clitoria ternatea*, which is well-known for having a high antioxidant content. Natural ingredients like Multani Mitti, sandalwood, aloe vera, honey, and rose water were used to make different batches. The physicochemical characteristics of the formulations, such as pH, spreadability, stability, appearance, and skin irritation, were assessed. Herbal face packs, which frequently combine multiple ingredients with complementary effects, improve skin tone, texture, and elasticity.^[44]

14. Skin lotion

The phenolic and flavonoid antioxidants found in butterfly pea flowers shield the skin from free radicals, which can cause oxidative damage. It has antioxidant properties and is made with triethanolamine (TEA) and stearic acid as emulsifiers and butterfly pea flower extract (BPFE). Formulations for lotions act as a barrier to stop free radicals from penetrating the

epidermis o the skin. Choosing a lotion that is both aesthetically pleasing and effective improves its appeal and guarantees that it satisfies the skin's protective requirements.^[45]

Table No. 3:- Research Findings on *Clitoria Ternatea*.

Sr. No.	Title	Author	Findings	Year
1.	Literature Study: The Effect of Telang Flower (<i>Clitoria ternatea</i> L.) on Human Health	Chylen Setiyo Rini et al.	(<i>Clitoria ternatea</i> L.) have great potential in supporting human health through their bioactive compound content, including flavonoids, anthocyanins, and alkaloids.	2025
2.	Formulation & Evaluation of Butterfly Pea Extract Loaded Nasal Spray for Treating Alzheimer's Disease	Shivaji Patel et al.	Nasal spray formulation made from <i>Clitoria Ternatea</i> shows excellent potential to become a new therapy option for Alzheimer's disease treatment.	2025
3.	Formulation and Evaluation of Hair Serum Using <i>Clitoria ternatea</i> and <i>Cyanthillium Cinereum</i> for Dandruff	Neethu Vijayan et al.	Prepared Hair Serum to alternate synthetic products, The serum exhibited effective antifungal activity	2025
4.	Formulation from Herbal Extract of <i>Clitoria ternatea</i> and its <i>In-vitro</i> Evaluation for Antidiabetic Activity.	Patil Suresh et al.	<i>Clitoria ternatea</i> –based herbal tea formulation showed strong in-vitro antidiabetic activity, with up to 94% α -amylase inhibition and 85% glucosidase inhibition, along with good physicochemical properties, making it a promising natural remedy for diabetes management	2024
5.	A Comprehensive Evaluation Of <i>Clitoria Ternatea</i> Its Botanical Description, Phytochemistry, Pharmacological Activities, And Traditional Uses	Santosh Kumar S.R. et al.	<i>Clitoria ternatea</i> , has been utilised in the medical field for a considerable amount of time and possesses a significant amount of potential for the future.	2024
6.	Formulation And Evaluation Of Antimicrobial Gel Of <i>Clitoria Ternatea</i> (Flowers)	Gauri V.Vaishnav et al.	The antimicrobial topical gel of <i>Clitoria ternatea</i> formulation showed better antibacterial activity.	2023
7.	Formulation and evaluation of antimicrobial gel from methanolic leaf extract of <i>Clitoria ternatea</i> L.	Sayukta Pahurkar et al.	Prepared herbal gels of <i>Clitoria ternatea</i> leaves extract were significantly active against tested pathogens which was comparable with standard antibiotic.	2023
8.	<i>Clitoria ternatea</i> Flower and	Ribi	<i>Clitoria ternatea</i> flower petals	2023

	Its Bioactive Compounds: Potential Use as Microencapsulated Ingredient for Functional Foods	Ramadanti Multisona et al.	are rich in bioactive compounds with diverse therapeutic properties, making them valuable for functional foods and pharmaceuticals, while microencapsulation especially freeze drying enhances their stability, bioavailability, and safety for consumption.	
9.	Evaluation of anti-inflammatory and anti-arthritic property of ethanolic extract of <i>Clitoria ternatea</i>	K.P. Swathi et al.	The ethanolic extract of <i>Clitoria ternatea</i> root possesses significant anti-inflammatory and anti-arthritic activity.	2020
10.	Impact of ultrasound and conventional extraction techniques on bioactive compounds and biological activities of blue butterfly pea flower (<i>Clitoria ternatea</i> L.)	Arshad Mehmood et al.	Extraction of bioactive compounds and compare with conventional technique	2019

CONCLUSION

Clitoria ternatea is a plant with a wide range of traditional medicinal applications. The butterfly pea, or *Clitoria ternatea*, has been used for a long time in medicine and has a lot of potential for the future. *Clitoria ternatea* offers a thorough examination of the plant's many biological, nutritional, and therapeutic advantages, especially in relation to both conventional and contemporary healthcare systems. Herbal formulations have excellent patient compliance, delivery rates, and efficacy when used to treat a range of disorders. Extracts from plants and herbs are well known for their therapeutic potential and have been used to treat a wide range of serious illnesses all over the world. A collection of information supporting the pharmacological properties of this plant, its active ingredient, and its formulations is provided above.

REFERENCES

1. Chauhan ES, Bist R. International Journal of Green and Harnessing the medicinal importance of *Clitoria ternatea* for diseases and beyond : a review of its phytochemistry and. 2024; (August 2018).
2. Al-Snafi AE. Pharmacological importance of *Clitoria ternatea*-A review. IOSR J Pharm., www.iosrphr.org [Internet]. 2016; 6(3): 68–83. Available from: www.iosrphr.org

3. Wanjari AS, Wanjari DS. An Overview on Herbal Medicine. Res., J Pharmacogn Phytochem., 2019; 11(1): 14.
4. Flowers T, Vaishnav G V, Chavan GC, Shirsat MK. Formulation And Evaluation Of Antimicrobial Gel Of Clitoria Formulation And Evaluation Of Antimicrobial Gel Of Clitoria Ternatea (Flowers). 2023; (July).
5. Deka M, Kalita JC. Preliminary Phytochemical Analysis and Acute Oral Toxicity Study of Mucuna Pruriens Linn. in Albino Mice. Int., Res., J Pharm., [Internet]. 2012; 3(2): 181–3. Available from: www.irjponline.com.
6. Singh KB. Medicinal Plants and Its Therapeutic Uses. Medicinal Plants and Its Therapeutic Uses. 2017.
7. Jain RA, Shukla SH. No TitlePharmacognostic Evaluation and Phytochemical Studies on Stem of Clitoria ternatea linn. Pharmacogn J. 2011; 3(24): 62–6.
8. Rampalli S, Gopalkrishnan B. Pharmacognostical investigation of Clitoria ternatea L. leaves. Plant Sci., Today. 2022; 9(4): 814–9.
9. Mukherjee PK, Kumar V, Kumar NS, Heinrich M. The Ayurvedic medicine Clitoria ternatea—From traditional use to scientific assessment. J Ethnopharmacol [Internet]. 2008 Dec; 120(3): 291–301. Available from: <https://linkinghub.elsevier.com/retrieve/pii/S0378874108004911>.
10. Parthiban R., Priyadarshini R., Mohanraj S., Mukesh Krishna A. P V., N. SM and D. World Journal of Pharmaceutical Research. World J Pharm., Res., 2024; 13(14): 551–9.
11. Alok S, Gupta N, Kumar A, Malik A. an Update on Ayurvedic Herb Vishnukanta Clitoria Ternatea Linn.): a Review. Int J Life Sci., Rev., 1 IJLSR [Internet]. 2015; 1(1): 1–9. Available from: <http://dx.doi.org/10.13040/IJPSR.0975-8232.IJLSR.1>
12. Pahurkar S, Pawar P. Formulation and evaluation of antimicrobial gel from methanolic leaf extract of Clitoria ternatea L., 2023; 8(7).
13. Gomez SM, . AK. Butterfly Pea (Clitoria ternatea): A Nutritive Multipurpose Forage Legume for the Tropics - An Overview. Pakistan J Nutr., 2003; 2(6): 374–9.
14. Ragupathy S, Newmaster SG. Valorizing the “Irulas” traditional knowledge of medicinal plants in the Kodiakkarai Reserve Forest, India. J Ethnobiol Ethnomed. 2009; 5: 1–13.
15. Veluchamy Balakrishnan, P. Prema, KC Ravindran, J. Philip Robinson. Ethnobotanical Studies among Villagers from Dharapuram Taluk, Tamil Nadu, India. Glob., J Pharmacol., 2009; (June): 08–14.
16. Gollen B, Mehla J, Gupta P. Pharmacological Potential of Clitoria ternatea Linn : Perspectives on Its Future as a Therapeutic Herbal Medicine. 2024; 1–8.

17. Mishra P, Singh A. EPRA International Journal of Research and Development (IJRD) CLITORIATERNATEA : A MAGICAL HERB IN WOUND HEALING TREATMENT Prateek Mishra, Ankit Singh EPRA International Journal of Research and Development (IJRD). 2022; 7838(May).
18. Taranalli AD, Cheeramkuzhy TC. Influence of Clitoria Ternatea Extracts on Memory and Central Cholinergic Activity in Rats. 2011; 0209.
19. Raghu KS, Shamprasad BR, Kabekkodu SP, Paladhi P, Joshi MB, Valiathan MS, et al. Age dependent neuroprotective effects of medhya rasayana prepared from Clitoria ternatea Linn. in stress induced rat brain. J Ethnopharmacol. 2017; 197: 173–83.
20. Neeti N Jain, C.C Ohal, S.K Shroff, R.H Bhutada, R.S Somani, V.S Kasture S. K. Clitoria ternatea and the CNS. J Pharmacol., 2003; 75(3): 529–36.
21. Margret AA, Begum TN, Parthasarathy S, Suvaitenamudhan S. A Strategy to Employ Clitoria ternatea as a Prospective Brain Drug Confronting Monoamine Oxidase (MAO) Against Neurodegenerative Diseases and Depression. Nat Products Bioprospect. 2015; 5(6): 293–306.
22. Rai SS, Banik A, Singh A, Singh M. Evaluation of Anti-Ulcer Activity of Aqueous and Ethanolic Extract of Whole Plant of Clitoria Ternatea in Albino Wistar Rats. Int J Pharm., Sci., Drug Res., 2015; 7(1): 33–9.
23. Kamilla L, Ramanathan S, Sasidharan S, Mansor SM. Evaluation of antinociceptive effect of methanolic leaf and root extracts of Clitoria ternatea Linn. In rats. Indian J Pharmacol. 2014; 46(5): 515–20.
24. Vimal Nair, Woo Young Bang, Elisa Schreckinger, Nuri Andarwulan LCZ. Protective Role of Ternatin Anthocyanins and Quercetin Glycosides from Butterfly Pea (Clitoria ternatea Leguminosae) Blue Flower Petals against Lipopolysaccharide (LPS)-Induced Inflammation in Macrophage Cells. J Agric., food Chem., 2015; 63(28).
25. Dnyaneshwar J. Taur RYP. Evaluation of antiasthmatic activity of Clitoria ternatea L. roots. J Ethnopharmacol. 2011; 2(136): 374–6.
26. Chayaratanasin P, Barbieri MA, Suanpairintr N, Adisakwattana S. Inhibitory effect of Clitoria ternatea flower petal extract on fructose-induced protein glycation and oxidation-dependent damages to albumin in vitro. BMC Complement Altern., Med., 2015; 15(1): 1–9.
27. Nithianantham K, Shyamala M, Chen Y, Latha LY, Jothy SL, Sasidharan S. Hepatoprotective potential of clitoria ternatea leaf extract against paracetamol induced damage in mice. Molecules. 2011; 16(12): 10134–45.

28. Nguyen KNT, Nguyen GKT, Nguyen PQT, Ang KH, Dedon PC, Tam JP. Immunostimulating and Gram-negative-specific antibacterial cyclotides from the butterfly pea (*Clitoria ternatea*). *FEBS J.* 2016; 283(11): 2067–90.
29. Iamsaard S, Burawat J, Kanla P, Arun S, Sukhorum W, Sripanidkulchai B, et al. Antioxidant activity and protective effect of *Clitoria ternatea* flower extract on testicular damage induced by ketoconazole in rats. *J Zhejiang Univ., Sci., B.* 2014; 15(6): 548–55.
30. Zhang S, Xiao KZ, Jin J, Zhang Y, Zhou W. Chemosensitizing activities of cyclotides from *clitoria ternatea* in paclitaxel-resistant lung cancer cells. *Oncol., Lett.,* 2013; 5(2): 641–4.
31. Taranalli AD, Cheeramkuzhy TC. Influence of *Clitoria ternatea* extracts on memory and central cholinergic activity in rats. *Pharm., Biol.,* 2000; 38(1): 51–6.
32. Maity N, Nema N, Sarkar B, Mukherjee P. Standardized *Clitoria ternatea* leaf extract as hyaluronidase, elastase and matrix-metalloproteinase-1 inhibitor. *Indian J Pharmacol.,* 2012; 44(5): 584–7.
33. Mohape Vaishali R, Kanase Jyoti A, Wakchaure Sayali M, Prof. Tambe S. E. Formulation and Evaluation of Polyherbal Anti-Aging Cream of *Clitoria Ternatea*, *Mangifera Indica* and *Annona Squamosa*. *Int J Adv., Res., Sci., Commun Technol.,* 2022; 2(5): 14–23.
34. Sharma U, Dwivedi S. Development and Characterization of Herbal Formulation Containing Aqueous Extract of *Clitoria Ternatea* Linn. (Flowers) for the Treatment of Vaginal Infection. 2021; 235–40.
35. Vijayan MN, Ansiya A AA, Hussainar F, Fathima K K FKK, Hadiya C Kabeer HCK, Ansar R. Formulation and Evaluation of Hair Serum Using *Clitoria Ternatea* and *Cyanthillium Cinereum* for Dandruff. *Int J Pharm., Res., Appl.,* 2025; 10(1): 541–8.
36. Neha Yadav PG. Formulation and Evaluation of *Clitoria ternatea* and *Nyctanthes arbor-tristis* Emulgel for Topical Drug Delivery. *Internatonal J Pharm., Sci.,* 2023; 2(11).
37. Pratiksha Gore, Mithun Maniyar, Vrunal More AK. FORMULATION AND EVALUATION OF POLYHERBAL TEA CONTAINING OF CLITORIA TERNATEA, YERBA MATE, ASHWAGANDHA FOR DIABETES, HEART DISEASE. *Int., J Innov., Stud.,* 2024.
38. Drisya. Formulation and Evaluation of Ethylacetate Leaf Extract of. *Foundry J.* 2024; 27(8): 138–49.
39. Tengku SDIS. Assegaf, Nelva K. Jusuf, Yunita S. Pane MR, Endang H. Darmani, Mustafa M. Amin RDL and AB. Anti-dandruff effects of butterfly pea flowers (*Clitoria*

- ernatea)-based shampoo: A pretest-posttest control study. 2024; 4(2).
40. Panda S. Formulation and Evaluation Clitoria Ternatea Linn. Biol., Life Sci., 2018; 5(October 2018): 51–5.
 41. Patel S, Wamankar S, Kumar Nema R. Formulation & Evaluation of Butterfly Pea Extract Loaded Nasal Spray for Treating Alzheimer's Disease. Int., J Adv., Multidiscip., Res., Stud., 2025; 5(3): 871–5.
 42. ANUGRAHANI AD, INDARTO D, PAMUNGKASARI EP, WIJAYANTI L, UTAMI F. Development of anti-obesity herbal drink from butterfly pea flower (*Clitoria ternatea*) extract and lemon (*Citrus limon*) juice. Nusant Biosci., 2025; 17(1): 129–36.
 43. Chetan N. Chaudhari, Dhammadip M. Vinkar DVA, Dhananjay V. Kayande, Dnyaneshwar V. Kayande OSK and DP, Tathe R. FORMULATION & EVALUTION OF HERBAL SUNCREEN UTILIZING BLUE PEA FLOWER. World J Pharm., Res., 2025; 14(14).
 44. Chaudhari P, Jirekarl J, Kathale K, More J, Sinhal A, Salunkhe A. Formulation and evaluation of an herbal face pack containing *Clitoria ternatea* for topical application. Int J Pharmacol Pharm., Res., 2025; 7(1): 32–5.
 45. Wikantyasning ER, Wahyuni TT. OPTIMIZATION AND FORMULATION OF SKIN LOTION CONTAINING BUTTERFLY PEA (*Clitoria ternatea*) FLOWER EXTRACT AND STUDY ON ITS ANTIOXIDANT ACTIVITY. BIO., Web Conf., 2024; 135: 0–7.